

CHROMIUM CHROMATE.

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Chromium chromate has been prepared from chromic chloride solution and silver chromate by double decomposition. The substance forms a brown glassy mass in the dry state, which is soluble in water. A study of the physical properties of its aqueous solution, such as the measurement of equivalent conductivity, freezing point, p_H value, magnetic susceptibility and absorption spectra, as well as of its chemical properties, shows that it is not a simple chromic chromate, $Cr_2(CrO_4)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$, but contains a complex chromato-chromiate anion and should be represented as $Cr \left[Cr \begin{matrix} (CrO_4)_3 \\ (H_2O)_3 \end{matrix} \right]$.

Chromates and sulphates, as is well known, behave chemically alike in many respects. Some chromates and sulphates are isomorphous and form mixed crystals. As chromium sulphates are known to form a well defined series of complex salts, it was considered worthwhile to investigate if similar chromium chromates might be prepared. Normal chromic chromate like normal and simple chromic sulphate is unknown. A number of oxides, such as Cr_5O_9 , CrO_2 , Cr_5O_{12} etc., with composition intermediate between chromic oxides, Cr_2O_3 , and chromic anhydride, CrO_3 , have been described in literature as chromium chromates. All these compounds arise either by partial oxidation of chromic hydroxide or by partial reduction of chromium trioxide, or by the interaction of chromic salts and chromates.

Brown coloured Cr_5O_9 , or $2Cr_2O_3 \cdot CrO_3$, was prepared by heating chromyl chloride vapour or chromium trioxide to 300° (Wöhler and Neger, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1859, iii, 56, 501). A hydrated variety, $2Cr_2O_3 \cdot CrO_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ was described by Popp (*Annalen*, 1890, 156, 93), who prepared it by boiling a mixture of potassium dichromate and sodium thiosulphate solution. The brown compound, $2Cr_2O_3 \cdot CrO_3$ was also obtained by Le Blanc by mixing solutions of neutral chromate and trivalent chromium salt (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1926, x, 6, 182). Anhydrous chromium dioxide CrO_2 or $Cr_2O_3 \cdot CrO_3$ was prepared by evaporating the solution of Cr_2O_3 in nitric acid and heating the residue to 290° (Jonitschwitsch, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, 3, 40). This and the previous compound are regarded as basic chromium chromate. Normal chromic chromate, Cr_5O_{12} or $Cr_2O_3 \cdot 3CrO_3$, or $Cr_2(CrO_4)_3$ was prepared by heating CrO_3 to 250° (Traube, *Annalen*, 1848, 66, 87; Rothaug, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, 84, 165; Simon and Schmidt, *ibid.*, 1924, 152, 191). It was converted into a soluble modification by keeping in contact with water for a long time.

Paneth mentions that if an excess of silver chromate is treated with a solution of chromic chloride, the colour of the solution turns reddish brown. On evaporating the filtrate from silver chloride a dark brown lustrous colloidal solid or varnish is left. This, on analysis, gave a ratio of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} as 2:3 (Paneth, "Radioelements as Indicators", 1928, p. 48, footnote). With a view to study the nature and composition of the product thus cursorily reported and to test the validity of the conclusions arrived at by previous workers on the subject, the present investigation was undertaken.

The filtrate from the double decomposition of silver chromate and chromic chloride solution was evaporated to dryness in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The product, which is soluble in water, was examined both by chemical and physical methods. Measurement of conductivity of its aqueous solution, determination of its molecular weight and magnetic susceptibility as well as a qualitative study of its absorption spectra seem to suggest that the substance is not a simple chromate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, but contains a complex chromato-chromiate anion besides the simple Cr^{3+} cation. Its constitution should, therefore, be represented by the formula

In the latter case the complex is represented as a triquo-trichromato-chromiate anion with the chromate group occupying only one co-ordination position. This is also supported by the general chemical behaviour of the substance.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Freshly prepared pure silver chromate in excess was triturated in a mortar with a concentrated solution of chromic chloride. The deep brown filtrate from silver chloride and excess of silver chromate on evaporation in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 gave a dark brown glassy mass. The latter on analysis gave a ratio between Cr^{III} : Cr^{VI} as 2:3. Chromatic chromium (Cr^{VI}) was determined by iodimetry. Total chromium was also estimated similarly after fusion with sodium peroxide. From the two results chromium present as Cr^{III} was calculated.

The solid substance was digested with glacial acetic acid several times at the room temperature. The solid was then dried in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 and solid KOH to a constant weight. The dry substance was analysed. (Found: CrO_3 , 59.75; Cr_2O_3 , 29.96. $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{CrO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires CrO_3 , 59.50; Cr_2O_3 , 30.0 per cent).

Cryoscopic Measurement.

Measurement of the molecular weight of the substance in aqueous solution by the freezing point method gave the following results.

Substance g/100 c.c. (on anhy- drous basis).	Depression Δ ($^{\circ}$ C)	Mol. wt. (<i>m</i> .)	Vant Hoff's factor ($i = M/m$).
2.4530	0.21	210.3	2.141
1.2265	0.12	184.05	2.401
0.61325	0.065	169.82	2.66

The results are more in favour of the constitution $\text{Cr}[\text{Cr}(\text{CrO}_4)_3]$ or $\text{Cr} \left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{CrO}_4)_3 \\ (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 \end{array} \right]$, which should dissociate into two ions, than of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3$, which would dissociate into five ions. Partial dissociation of the complex chromato-chromiate or aquochromato-chromiate anion, increasing with dilution, is also indicated.

Equivalent Conductivity at 25 $^{\circ}$.

The above conclusion is supported also by the measurement of the equivalent conductivity of solutions of the substance, assuming it to be a binary ter-tervalent electrolyte based on the formula $\text{Cr}[\text{Cr}(\text{CrO}_4)_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or

ν (dilution) ...	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ , ...	65.51	72.40	80.89	87.10	88.69	89.86

Measurement of ϕ_{H} value in N/15-solution of the Substance.

An N/15-solution of the substance was prepared containing 1/90th of the formula weight of the substance per litre. ϕ_{H} value of this solution and of an equivalent solution of chromic acid as well as of N/10-chromic chloride and hydrochloric acid were measured at room temperature by means of glass electrode for the purpose of comparison. The results are given below.

	N/10-CrCl ₃	N/10-HCl	N/15-H ₂ CrO ₄	N/15-Substance
ϕ_{H}	1.25	1.04	1.82	2.87

The p_n of the solution of the substance is much higher than that of an equivalent solution of chromic acid which would not have been the case if it were simply normal chromic chromate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3$, as the latter, representing a salt of a very weak base and a weak acid, would have hydrolysed more or less completely in solution giving a p_n value almost equal to that of chromic acid. The p_n value of $N/10\text{-CrCl}_3$ is found to approach more closely that of hydrochloric acid of the same equivalent strength though HCl is much stronger acid than H_2CrO_4 .

Magnetic Susceptibility.

The susceptibility of the substance was determined in a Curie's balance at 30° .

$\chi_m = 18.95 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m = 506 \times 18.95 \times 10^{-6} = 9588.7 \times 10^{-6}$. From which $\chi_a = 1942.72 \times 10^6$, and $p_{\text{Weiss}} = 10.79$ per g. atom of Cr.

This is more or less in agreement with the value that might be deduced either for $\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Cr} \left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{CrO}_4)_3 \\ \text{Cr} \\ (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 \end{array} \right]$, which should be 8.9, as chromium, either as a simple or a complex trivalent ion, has got the same magnetic moment of 19.0 Weiss magneton, and a moment of 2.2 Weiss magneton in the form of $\text{CrO}_4^{=}$ anion.

Absorption Spectra.

The absorption spectra of the substance in aqueous solution is entirely different from those of chromic chloride, chromic acid, potassium chromate and dichromate. Solutions having the same theoretical concentration of Cr^{3+} ions for the chromic chloride and the substance were employed for comparison, as also the solutions having the same theoretical concentration of $\text{CrO}_4^{=}$ ions for the substance, chromic acid, potassium chromate and dichromate. The difference is evident from the following Plates I and II.

The solution of the substance was made on the assumption that it was a simple chromic chromate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Time of exposure (15 sec.) and the thickness of the solutions (1 cm.) in the cell were kept constant in all cases. The strength of the chromic chloride solution employed was $N/10$, the strength of the solution of the substance was adjusted accordingly.

The strengths of the solutions of chromic acid, potassium chromate and dichromate were so adjusted that the concentration of Cr^{VI} in them was equal to that of the chromic chromate solution. A glance at the absorption spectra in the above plates shows that the substance possesses a strong general absorption in the visible from 5750 \AA onwards and also a general absorption towards the extreme red beyond 6600 \AA . In other words, the substance in aqueous solution shows only a limited range of transmission between $5750\text{--}6600 \text{ \AA}$ in the visible.

It may, therefore, be concluded that the solution of the substance must at least contain an ion other than Cr^{+++} and CrO_4^{--} or $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$.

The substance also shows some characteristic chemical behaviour. It dissolves very slowly in cold water but more rapidly in hot water. The solution gives a brownish precipitate on boiling. A dilute solution of the substance gives no precipitate in the cold with silver nitrate solution, but precipitates red silver chromate with excess of the reagent. Solutions of barium chloride and lead acetate give a brown precipitate. Aqueous ammonia decomposes it with precipitation of chromic hydroxide.

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FIG. 1.

Chromic chloride→
Substance→
Iron arc→
Chromic acid→

FIG. 2.

Pot. chromate→
Iron arc→
Substance→
Iron arc→
Pot. dichromate→
Chromic acid→

